

EXEMPLAR CASE STUDIES OF AVIATION NOISE MITIGATION STRATEGIES IN THE EUROPEAN UNION: A REVIEW OF THE COMMUNICATION AND ENGAGEMENT STATE OF THE ART

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ABSTRACT:

Environmental noise from aviation represents a significant health burden for citizens and a major constraint to airport development. Industry has responded through noise abatement interventions, however research conducted in the ANIMA Project suggests non-acoustic factors are central to the human health response to noise, and that many of these factors can be influenced by airports engaging with their communities.

This paper presents the results of a series of case studies seeking to understand the state of the art in noise communications undertaken by European Member State airports, comparing them to what the literature suggests is 'Best Practice'.

Current practices are found to be comprehensive, but lacking in a number of key areas, suggesting the industry can enhance the quality of its communication activities and have a positive influence on the role of non-acoustic factors in driving noise annoyance.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

The health impacts of aviation noise are significant and well documented [1–3], with stress-related effects outside the hearing system playing a key role in health outcomes such as, sleep disturbance, cardiovascular diseases, and cognitive impairment in children [4,5]. A key determinant in such factors is annoyance, defined as a feeling of displeasure, nuisance, disturbance or irritation caused by a

specific sound [6]. The role of annoyance is so strong that the World Health Organisation Environmental Noise Guidelines [1] consider it as a noise associated health outcome in its own right. This claim is supported by the ANIMA Project [5] with both reports highlighting the importance of addressing annoyance (and sleep disturbance) as the most critical outcomes of noise. This is based on the understanding that “on the one hand they represent direct disturbance and irritation to residents living near airports, and on the other hand persistent annoyance and sleep disturbance have been linked to other adverse health effects through the stress mechanism” [5].

1.2. Non-acoustic factors and the role of communication and engagement.

ANIMA [4] performed a review of the academic literature surrounding the human response to noise, finding that acoustical factors, explain only a part of the annoyance response to noise, and that “non-noise-related characteristics of the person or environment play a crucial role in the formation and explanation of noise annoyance” [4]. Following the work of Vader [7], such non-acoustic factors were found in not only to play a key role in annoyance, but also to be open to influence by airports, with 7 non-acoustic factors found to play a strong role in annoyance, and being open to modification. The nature of these factors (i.e. attitude towards the noise source, choice in insulation, trust) has seen the industry identify communication and engagement as key elements in the management of noise impact - see for example: Federal Aviation Authority [8,9]; Airport Cooperative Research Program [10]; Canadian Airports Council [11]; European Economic and Social Committee [12]; Eurocontrol [13]; Sustainable Aviation [14,15]; 2014; and Civil Air Navigation Service Organisation (CANSO) [16,17]. Moreover, when re-visiting their 4

core principles of the Balanced Approach [18] in 2007, ICAO added a '5th Pillar' – 'People issues'. This commitment was later developed further in Circular 351 – Community Engagement for Aviation Environmental Management [19].

1.3. Communication and Engagement Best Practice

Gardner et al. [20] defined the term 'stakeholder' as "anyone with an interest in a particular decision" and 'stakeholder engagement' "any process that involves stakeholders in some form of collaborative effort directed towards a decision, which might involve future planning and/or behaviour change." It is about the "building of relationships with people and putting those relationships to work to accomplish shared goals, i.e. involving those who are at the heart of the change we wish to see" [21].

Such engagement can take place through a variety of levels, often including communication and engagement, but also at higher, more participatory levels. Arnstein [22] illustrates this through her 'Ladder of Citizen Participation', in which 8 levels of participation were categorised into three groupings:

1. Non-Participation
 - a. Manipulation
 - b. Therapy
2. Degrees of Tokenism
 - a. Informing
 - b. Consultation
 - c. Placation
3. Degrees of citizen power
 - a. Partnerships
 - b. Delegated Power
 - c. Citizen Control

The latter levels imply that some degree of control is afforded to stakeholder groups, from the very beginning of any stakeholder engagement, implying a level of co-creation in any produced outputs (i.e. new knowledge, or implementing activities or projects to provide a solution to a given problem).

The importance of communication and engagement can be traced to the idea of public participation and the idea of the 'public sphere', first used by German philosopher Jürgen Habermas (1962). Today, a range of established definitions are available [23–27]. Perhaps the most comprehensive is provided by Hanchey [28], who identified three main objectives of public participation, and seven second-order objectives (Figure 1). These outline the different functions of public engagement, emphasising not only its importance for the distribution of information, but its role in promoting community acceptance and diffusing conflict – key requirements of airport communication.

Figure 1: Objectives of Public Participation [28].

Such public participation has the ability to facilitate greater organisational transparency, and develop community trust in, and an understanding of, organisation activity. This thereby reduces stakeholder-business conflict, and can lead to "increasing the likelihood that environmental decisions are perceived to be holistic and fair, accounting for a diversity of values and needs, whilst recognising the complexity of human-environmental interactions" [26]. The concept lends itself to what Webler [29] termed 'social-learning', that is, when the public unite to solve a shared problem. Again, the relevance for airport community engagement here is clear, particularly when some communities stand to suffer from increased noise for the benefit of another. This also has parallels with Vader's modifiable non-acoustic factors of having a voice or influence over an issue – something only possible if opportunities are provided to influence the behaviour of the source (airports), leading to decisions that are perceived to be fairer [30].

Importantly, social-learning can help to develop cognitive enhancement ("the acquisition of knowledge") and moral development ("the reservation of personal and selfish requests in favour of actions which benefit society as a whole") [31]. This indicates a prominent role for public participation in an airports ability to obtain a licence to operate from those who express a higher degree of annoyance from aircraft noise. Webler also talks about the importance of fairness when seeking a consensus so that "equality and popular sovereignty can emerge and personal competence can develop" [21]. The importance of having a vision of what should be achieved from the public participation and how it will be accomplished is also stressed. Key requirements for fair and competent ideal speech are outlined in Table 1.

The implication of this is that:

- Communication should be underpinned by a 'common language' that is comprehensible to all.
- Access to expertise should be available to all.
- Decision-making processes are inclusive, transparent and allow the validity of claims to be challenged.

Table 1 : Conditions for fair and competent ideal speech situation [28]

Fairness	Competence
Anyone may participate	Minimal standards for cognitive and lingual competence
Assert validity claims	Access the knowledge
Challenge validity claims	Consensually-approved translation scheme
Influence final determinations of validity	Most reliable methodological techniques available

Asensio et al. [30] came to a similar conclusion, suggesting that airports must shift from information provision and limited consultation. Rather they should seek participation and empowerment if community engagement is to be genuine and influence the non-acoustical factors known to exacerbate annoyance responses. A further implication is that if participation is to be secured and meaningful (and thus likely to influence attributes like attitudes and perceptions of fairness and trust) then communication and engagement should relate to issues that affect the participants i.e. relate to noise management or wider QoL (Quality of Life) issues directly impacting on communities close to airports.

1.4. Emerging practice in the dissemination of information between ‘experts’ and their publics.

The theory described above is consistent with the emerging approaches in the science communication literature, a field that shares many similarities with airports seeing as it represents a group of ‘experts’ (scientists/airports) looking to engage with public stakeholders through the dissemination of data, on often complex issues.

The literature describes a traditional means of science communication under the ‘Public Understanding of Science’ (PUS) model. This model, often referred to as the ‘Deficit Model’, focuses on “increasing publics’ knowledge of scientific content and processes. This increase in knowledge is understood to occur via the transmission of scientific knowledge from the scientific community to individuals in society” [32]. PUS is today considered by many to be a ‘deficit’ model, being “built on the assumptions that the public is ignorant of scientific facts and processes, that science is neutral and objective and thus has the wisdom and answers to fill the deficit, and that ignorance of science is detrimental to a thriving society” [32]. As a result, and as illustrated in Table 2, the model has traditionally held researchers as the expert owners of a narrow set of typically quantitative data within established scientific

paradigms, where engagement takes place only through one-way dialogues which, although better than no communication, can often leave communities voiceless, disinterested, and discouraged [33]. This ‘deficit’ model has traditionally seen researchers only publish their works through academic papers, rather than engaging with their audiences to drive impact, and the evaluation of the impact of such work has seldomly been evaluated.

Table 2: ‘Public Understanding of Science’ – Deficit Model

Aims	To increase public appreciation for science by telling people more about science
Ownership	Scientific output is owned by the scientific community
Methods	One-way – tells people about science
Scope	Narrow – considers issues only within the scientific paradigm. Traditionally quantitative.
Starting position	Science is expert – people just need to understand and accept their wisdom
Impact and subsequent evaluation	A secondary concern. Evaluation rarely considered.

Recently, researchers in the field of science (i.e. data) communication have acknowledged the failings of this model. Increasingly they are advocating a new approach to communication and engagement to publics via the ‘Public Engagement with Science and Technology’ (PEST) model [34]. PEST is described as a ‘dialogue’ or ‘participation’ model in which publics and scientists both benefit from listening to and learning from one another, built on the assumption that both publics and scientists have expertise, valuable perspectives, and knowledge to contribute to the development of science and its application in society [34]. PEST does not discount the need for public citizens to learn from experts. It does however argue that “focus should be on the valuable perspectives and knowledge publics bring from their lives that enhance the discussions of science and issues of science-related societal issues”. As can be seen in Table 3, this model differs from the PUS model in a number of ways. The aim of the public communication and engagement includes elements of competence raising, not only of the data but also of its underlying methods. Data is seen as being owned by all of society, with meaning established based on publics interpretation of the data, and being able to contribute to it with their own voices and perspectives, through two-way dialogues. Importantly, any communication activities designed to deliver impact are conducted with a specific objective from the outset, and with means to evaluate impact considered from the onset of the

engagement, so as to understand before and after implications of the engagement.

Table 3: 'Public Engagement with Science and Technology' – Dialogue Model

Aims	To stimulate and inform discussion and to increase public awareness of scientific processes
Ownership	Scientific output is owned by society
Methods	Two-way – encourages feedback and discussion
Scope	Broad – considers science issues within various social contexts and allows values and feelings to be included. i.e. qualitative.
Starting position	Open minded – different parties will come with different views and a consensus will be reached
Impact and subsequent evaluation	A primary concern. Objectives of activities outlined from the start. Evaluation considered throughout.

1.5. Implications for airport noise management

All of the above implies that that the aviation industry should take a more considered approach to communication and engagement. This would include more effective processes of dialogue, competence raising, fairness, and the consideration of non-acoustic factors, including the use of qualitative data. This suggests that there are similarities between the industry and the transition between the PUS 'Deficit Model' and the PEST 'Dialogue Model'.

Following this emerging narrative, this paper assesses a number of case study airports in terms of their approach to communication and engagement surrounding a series of noise abatement interventions. The paper establishes the current state-of-the-art in terms of industry practice, and establishes where airports lie on 'Deficit-Dialogue' model spectrum. In so doing, the paper highlights the extent to which the industry is conforming to 'Best Practice', and makes recommendations for future research to support the industry in its efforts to help improve the QoL of its local residents by allaying noise impact borne by annoyance and its associated health impacts.

Section 2 describes the methodology taken in the work, with the results obtained found in Section 3. Section 4 presents a discussion of the findings, before Section 5 makes closing conclusions.

The work presented is part of a Horizon 2020 funded research project called ANIMA (Aviation Noise Impact Management through novel Approaches) [35] undertaken to better understand noise impact mitigation in the EU, with the aim of developing new methodologies, approaches and

tools to manage and mitigate the impact of aviation noise.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

As this research is rooted in a specific industry, comprising many organisations, and with many different actors, several different methodological approaches could have been appropriate. Based on a review of the literature [36–40], a decision was made to pursue a case study approach as the primary research methodology.

Case study research is particularly useful in instances where a researcher is looking to "investigate a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident" [27]. Case study research is an accepted and valid method within the field of organisational research [41], due to it being able to facilitate the building of theories, the development of concepts, the drawing of specific implications, and to contribute rich insights to support, or counter, existing material within the literature [36]. Additionally, the approach empowers the researcher to use a combination of several different data collection methods, both quantitative and qualitative in nature [37].

The research focuses on a narrow set of 'exemplar' case studies, based on rich qualitative data, rather than a quantitative analysis across a broader number of cases. Such an approach is important because, as described in ANIMA [42], all airports have different political, economic, environmental and cultural contexts that can influence which Balanced Approach interventions may be most appropriate in a given setting. This means that approaches taken by airports are likely to differ on a case by case basis, and that this may not reflect different levels of good practice, but may rather represent appropriate practice for each specific airport.

Specifically, for each exemplar airport, a review of publicly available documentation regarding each airport and its case intervention took place, followed by in-depth semi-structured interviews with airport representatives to understand in greater detail the different approaches taken in the implementation of each intervention. The interviews conducted were facilitated by local members of the research team to reflect their expertise, and to overcome language barriers. Doing so empowered the researchers to develop their own question protocol relevant to each specific case study, however guidance on the key aspects of each case to be investigated were outlined in advance to aid in the development of the specific interview protocols. Such protocols were

focused on the 'processes' behind the implementation of a given intervention:

- Identification of the need or opportunity for the intervention.
- The design of different intervention options.
- The selection of the chosen intervention.
- Its implementation.
- The extent of any subsequent post-implementation evaluation.

2.2. Case Selection

The selection of airport case studies was based on research industry contacts, and research partners in the ANIMA project. The case airports, and the specific interventions studied are listed below.

- *Barcelona El Prat (Spain)*: Barcelona Airport case study focuses mainly on the operational procedure. Specifically, it was related to the switching role of each runway during the day (the ones that would be used for take offs, should be used for landings and vice versa), and new flight configuration during the night.
- *Catania (Italy)*: Catania Airport is a land use focused case study, where noise-zoning legislation plays a key role.
- *Cluj-Napoca Avram Iancu (Romania)*: Cluj-Napoca Airport is currently undergoing major development in anticipation of future growth, with a new runway being built in phases to handle larger aircraft. This case study looks at the use of preferential runways and night restrictions at the airport to avoid over flying Cluj city centre.
- *Frankfurt (Germany)*: This case study looked at interventions and measures taken with respect to land-use planning.
- *London Heathrow (UK)*. This case study describes the implementation of a steeper departure profile with the intention of reducing noise impact over a community. The idea for the intervention was initially raised by community members.
- *Helsinki (Finland)*: This case study describes the implementation of a new operational procedure (NADP1) at the airport to reduce expected increases in noise exposure to residents from increasing capacity at RWY-22L.
- *Iasi (Romania)*: This land-use planning case study investigated impact of airport noise on surrounding communities and the approach taken to stakeholder engagement.
- *Kiev (Ukraine)*: This case study provides an overview of the previous, current and proposed practices of Boryspil International Airport (Kiev), as a part of their Noise

Management Strategies.

- *Ljubljana (Slovenia)*: This case study provides an overview of the previous, current and proposed practices of Ljubljana Airport, as a part of their Noise Management Strategies, included within annual Sustainability Reports.
- *Amsterdam Schiphol (The Netherlands)*: This case study looks at the implementation of a noise abatement operational procedure (NADP2) to provide noise relief to communities around Schiphol from both arriving and departing aircraft. At the same time, it was anticipated that this change would deliver fuel savings for airlines.
- *Stockholm-Arlanda (Sweden)*: This case study discusses the implications of a proposed curved approach to reduce noise impact in response to opening an additional runway at Stockholm Arlanda International Airport. The case study also discusses the impact of community engagement by airport authorities.
- *Vienna (Austria)*: This case study describes the implementation of a curved approach to Vienna Airport, within a pre-existing 'Dialogue Forum'.

3. KEY FINDINGS

On reviewing the case studies, a number of key findings and implications for airport noise management became clear and are presented in this section. Due to the number of case studies and their depth, detailed results of each are not listed here. Rather we present the key findings and core messages from their analysis. Full case studies and research data can be found in ANIMA Deliverable 2.5 [43].

3.1. Nature of the dialogue

The majority of cases illustrated some form of engagement, typically through consultation events between the airport and its stakeholders. In all cases, the airport took the dominant role as the 'expert', being the lead actor in determining what data was pertinent, how it was collected (via monitoring or modelling), and its subsequent dissemination.

The only significant deviations from this approach were at Heathrow, Vienna and Frankfurt. In the former the airport was responding to specific concerns from a community about the altitude of aircraft, and so a wide range of information was provided specifically to address citizen needs and concerns. Information was presented at a consultation event, however no official public report was made available. Although the data provided was in response to specific community needs, it was aviation stakeholders who determined which

information was relevant, which should be collected and how it should be presented. Non-acoustic factors were not considered or reported on.

At Vienna, the airport was also responding to a specific community claim, and also went about providing information and conducting trials based on community desires (as well as considering necessary technical and safety specifications). The 'Vienna Dialogue Forum' acts as a means through which the airport can regularly communicate with its stakeholders and to gain input into decision-making processes.

At Frankfurt, the Airport and Region Forum, established in 2008, took a similar approach as in Vienna, acting as an independent forum where the airport engages not as the 'expert' but merely as another stakeholder. Notably, the Forum's Board of Directors comprises 3 members – an independent, an airport representative, and a representative of towns and cities, ensuring that both the airport and the regions have equal representation at this level. The forum had significant success in 2011 with the launch of the NORAH Noise Impact Study ("Noise-Related Annoyance, Cognition, and Health"). Similar schemes were found at other airports, for example the 'Noise Technical Working Group' at Barcelona.

At Arlanda, a 'Virtual Community Noise Simulator' was used to help community members experience the noise situation of future flight path changes virtually. Using a post-use questionnaire perceived differences in the flight path changes were assessed, however the aim of the assessment was primarily to understand if the public could perceive changes in glide approach angle, rather than considering non-acoustic factors. Communities engaged were informed about different glide slope angles, and a joint decision was made about the location of the new flight procedure, demonstrating that community views were taken into consideration, and based on what was feasible.

Airports appeared to use noise metrics to describe the 'what' of a noise situation. To describe the 'why', consultation events with airport stakeholders tended to be used to explain the situation to small numbers of interested people. Non-acoustic factors were seldom considered in terms of data collection, although many of the stakeholders interviewed were aware of the importance of such factors and were considering them in decision-making on a more informal level.

3.2. Access to expertise

In terms of giving recipients access to expertise, Vienna did so through an independent employee of the National Air Navigation Service Provider Austro Control. This representative attends 'Dialogue

Forum' meetings to present data requested by members independently from the airport, with the objective of raising both transparency and trust in the data, whilst also acting as a means through which the data can be challenged. A similar approach was taken at Heathrow, where an external consultancy was used to collect and disseminate the data. Generally, the cases showed that the airport (and its industry partners) was the sole owner of data and the expert voice in any dialogues that took place. Other airports such as Arlanda and Barcelona took similar approaches, however only Vienna did so through a dedicated representative empowered to independently provide residents with any information they desired.

3.3. Transparency and inclusivity in the decision-making process.

The processes embedded in the 'Vienna Dialogue Forum' enabled a level of transparency in the decision-making process, as self-reported by interview participants. All members in the forum are empowered to engage in discussions, even if they are perceived to not directly be impacted by, say, a given intervention. At Heathrow, a level of inclusivity can be garnered from the fact that it was community concerns about low-flying aircraft over their community that was the impetus for the intervention and subsequent communication of trial data. This implies some level of two-way dialogue, and the lengths gone to by the airport to disseminate data through varied means and via an external agency suggests that transparency and inclusivity in the data was high. However, interviews with operational and noise managers highlighted that communities still did not trust the data provided and find it hard to understand more technical information relating to the feasibility of different departure procedures. As previously mentioned, Frankfurt are a further example of transparency and inclusivity in decision making, seeing as the group is independently lead, and that community groups are represented at the highest level of the Forum's Board of Directors. Within the Forum, the 'Environment and Neighbourhood House' acts as an observer of developments in the region, and a neutral information service provider and a mediator between the conflicting parties. A central task of the group is to carry out independent aircraft noise measurements and to make the results available to the public. To this aim it has its own network of 9 fixed and 2 mobile monitoring stations which are managed independently of the airports 29 stations.

3.4. Use of a common and comprehensible language.

The case studies demonstrated a range of purposes for which noise information was prepared and disseminated by the case study airports:

- Communicating aircraft noise issues to different stakeholder groups.
- Setting criteria and targets for regulatory purposes (and monitoring compliance).
- Comparing alternative what-if scenarios (i.e. between one intervention and another).

Setting criteria and targets for regulatory purposes was conducted in the Frankfurt case study where examples are provided of how acoustic metrics have informed a complex set of operating restrictions and compensation plans designed to manage the impact of airport expansion. Similarly, the Barcelona case study highlights the challenges of managing the impact of airport expansion, whilst the Catania case study used aggregate metrics generated by a mix of models and monitoring tools to justify zoning for land-use planning and compensation.

Comparing alternative what-if scenarios was a common purpose for noise data collection and dissemination. At Helsinki for example data was used to ascertain the impacts of different operating procedures (alternative departure procedures). At Arlanda data was used to investigate the impacts of implementing steeper arrival glide slopes. In Vienna and Schiphol, a curved approach and amendments to NADPs used were investigated respectively.

The Heathrow, Vienna and Frankfurt cases represent cases where data was not only used to investigate the potential impacts of different operating procedures, but also to drive significant community engagement with local community action groups, thus leading to better citizen engagement.

In terms of the amount of information provided, Heathrow and Vienna produced a significant amount of data relevant to each specific case, with both basing their data acquisition on resident concerns – Vienna and Frankfurt going as far as performing additional monitoring of trial data based on specific resident requests. Heathrow presented their data via a consultation event in the affected community that raised the idea for the work, but nowhere else. The data presented was detailed and pertinent without being onerous, however it was not made available on-line after the event. At Vienna, the data regarding the specific intervention was disseminated at 'Forum events', and noise data is published more generally in quarterly and annual reporting. The airport acknowledged the importance of only providing pertinent information by recently reducing the size of annual reporting from 133 pages in 2016 pages to just 32 in 2018, in an attempt to avoid data overload.

3.5. Two-Way Dialogues

Only Vienna Airport was using a system that could

be described as being truly two-way, where levels of expertise were levelled and where all participants had a voice. This was made possible through the 'Dialogue Forum', and its being driven by vision agreed by all stakeholders, which acknowledged noise as a challenge for the airport to address, but also the vital role of the airport to the regional economy. Some level of two-way dialogues was found at Heathrow in that the operational change was raised by citizens and addressed by the airport, but dialogues that took place saw the airport retain its perspective as the data owner and expert in the dialogue. At best the airport could be described as responding to citizen requests, rather than engaging in a thorough process of on-going dialogue.

Although other cases illustrated some consideration of two-way dialogues they focused more on a request-data provision level rather than genuine two-way discussions in which hierarchies were levelled and through which genuine two-way discussions could take place.

3.6. Evaluation of Non-Acoustic Factors

No in-depth consideration of non-acoustic factors was identified in any of the case studies, beyond anecdotal acknowledgement of the role played by such factors. No pre- or post- evaluation regarding such factors was highlighted, and interventions appeared to happen in an unstructured way with no set guidance followed, other than some basic principles in the 'Vienna Dialogue Forum', and standardised processes involving dialogue with industry stakeholders. Intervention success was based purely on acoustic factors, other than noise-related complaints from communities.

4. DISCUSSION

The case studies conducted in this research identified that communication and engagement with stakeholders takes place across airports of all size, regardless of their geographic location, or the Balanced Approach element being implemented.

Previous ANIMA research has categorised airports as being either Pathfinders (at the forefront of noise management), Experienced Travellers (engaging with noise management but not at the cutting-edge), and Starting the Journey Airports (only just beginning to understand and address noise issues). These case studies found that although Pathfinders did have evidence of more developed noise management practices, and in general airports acknowledged the importance of communication and engagement, they lacked any sort of systematic approach in how to carry it out. This is certainly in terms of compliance with ideas described under the 'Public Engagement and Science and Technology' (PEST) communication model. Taking the

framework used in Tables 2 and 3, existing airport communication and engagement approaches can be illustrated. As Table 4 shows, such approaches closely mirror that of the PUS 'Deficit Model' of communication.

Table 4: Traditional Airport perspectives on 'knowledge' and communication

Aims	Tell stakeholders 'what' is happening.
Ownership	Important data and knowledge owned by aviation stakeholders.
Methods	One-Way (Airport -> Resident)
Scope	Narrow - only considers noise data so as to describe the 'what'.
Starting position	Airport is Expert. Data is data.
Impact and subsequent evaluation	Little evaluation beyond those measured by noise metrics that are often confusing and meaningless to community members. Communication and engagement activities take place with no stated objective.

Airports too often communicate solely with the reason of explaining what is happening, using technical data derived from their own understanding of noise, rather than explaining what is happening and why, based on the needs and understandings of communities. This limits the opportunity for comprehension, and can act as a barrier to developing fair outcomes and in developing trust in the data given. To compound this, dialogues were found to be too often one-way in nature, with the airport starting in an expert position. This was found to be the case even when airports were acting on an intervention that was suggested by communities, or where airports had gone through significant engagement and communication activities. Non-acoustic factors were rarely considered by airports, with none demonstrating any qualitative evaluation regarding the impact of interventions on resident health, well-being and QoL. The impression is that many interventions take place purely to appease the vocal minority of residents who complain about noise, with the impact on and the perspectives of the wider community seldom evaluated. Communication 'Best Practice' also suggests that any engagement should have a stated purpose and goal, however little evidence of this was found other than merely passing on information regarding each specific intervention.

If we again take the framework provided in Tables 1 and 2 regarding effective communication and engagement, we can imply a number of key implications for effective airport communication and engagement in the future.

Table 5: Implications for airport communication and engagement.

Aims	Tell stakeholders 'why' things are happening and obtain their input to inform decisions. Aim to increase competence and produce fair outcomes.
Ownership	Important data and knowledge owned by society (i.e. via non-acoustic factors)
Methods	Two-Way (Airport <-> Resident)
Scope	Wide - considers a range of socio-economic and cultural factors to explain the 'why' and understand the 'what then'.
Starting position	Open minded - different stakeholders offer their own expertise and views to be shared. A consensus can be reached.
Impact and subsequent evaluation	Tell stakeholders 'why' things are happening and obtain their input to inform decisions.

Airports need to think more about why they are explaining things to their communities and what the intention or goal of each communication is – with concepts of competence raising and fairness playing a vital role. Central to this is two-way dialogues that aim to level expertise and consider all perspectives equally so as to engender trust in industry stakeholders and their intentions – whilst also helping to increase the competence of citizens in understanding what types of interventions might be feasible, and why certain decisions are made. Moreover, citizens need to be able to challenge the data they are given and request their own data analyses so that they are able to fully understand the information they are being provided.

Airports must acknowledge the vital role of non-acoustic factors in allaying the human response to noise, and in so doing, seek to capture this information from citizens, both before and after engagements or interventions have been implemented so that their effectiveness can be assessed.

What is also clear from the findings is that whilst airports are demonstrating that they are committed to effective noise management and are exploring increasingly sophisticated noise abatement interventions and communication techniques, approaches to the implementation of interventions, and any subsequent communication and engagement appears to be relatively unstructured and conducted in an ad-hoc manner. On the one hand, this is both to be expected and advisable – each airport faces its own specific noise challenges and finds itself in a specific setting in which to overcome them. The research showed that the process of a noise management intervention being

implemented broadly follows a five-step process:

1. Identifying the need for an intervention.
2. Designing a range of intervention options.
3. Selecting the most appropriate intervention.
4. Implementing the intervention.
5. Conducting post-implementation evaluation.

We believe that the identification of some core principles to drive each of these phases could have value for the industry, and that communication and engagement should play a key role throughout, for example: by listening to communities to understand if they are happy with the noise situation and seeking their input on how it could be improved; by understanding which factors need to be considered in the design of different options, ideally giving citizens the ability to inform on such designs; by empowering communities to be able to actively play a role in the selection of given intervention options, and canvassing residents to understand how effective the intervention was at addressing non-acoustic factors.

We propose that rather than being a 5th pillar of the Balanced Approach, Communication and Engagement sits across all existing Balanced Approach interventions and across all phases of their implementation, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The theoretical place of communication and engagement in the Balanced Approach to noise management at an airport [43].

Vienna can perhaps be considered as the best example of engagement from the cases considered, with the 'Dialogue Forum' being illustrative of a number of elements of 'Best Practice':

- The 'Forum' operates independently from the airport and comprises all stakeholders (i.e. aviation industry, local authorities, local communities).

- All communities given a voice to speak and provide input, even if an issue concerns other communities.
- The forum operates on an agreed vision in which the communities acknowledged the importance of the airport to the local region, and the airport acknowledges a requirement to improve the noise environment.
- Data is provided in on request by dedicated person from the Air Navigation Service Provider rather than from the airport. The data is presented by the representative in person and community members are given the opportunity to question the data provided.
- Short, quarterly noise reports are presented, together with a letter from the 'Dialogue Forum' leader. These are supplemented by larger annual reports – recently reduced in size from almost 140 pages to approximately 30 to prevent data overload and ensure that only pertinent information is provided.

Austro Control ensuring the resources for a dedicated person to work for the 'Dialogue Forum' independently from the airport showed a great deal of commitment to fostering good communication with residents. Having a single responsible person has also enabled the representative to have a long-standing relationship with residents, helping to build trust.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The case studies carried out in this research illustrate a wide range of different practices and procedures regarding the implementation of different Balanced Approach interventions in European Airports, demonstrating the significant efforts that the aviation industry is going to in order to help mitigate its noise impact and exposure. Efforts span the entire range of Balanced Approach elements, and there is evidence of a maturing landscape driven by richer stakeholder communication and engagement.

The case studies demonstrate considerable efforts have been undertaken by airports to communicate with their communities. However, the methods and strategies underpinning these efforts were found to not comply with what the literature suggests is best practice. Communication and engagement interventions appear to be implemented in a relatively haphazard manner: typically responding to a given local issue or noise management intervention, rather than being part of a systematic and considered communications strategy with targeted and evaluated outcomes.

The research also found that airports are only just beginning their journey towards communication and engagement under what could be described as the

PEST 'Dialogue Model' of communication and engagement. Dialogues remain relatively one-way, planning of communication and engagement interventions appear to be unguided, and there is little evidence of the impact of Balanced Approach or communication and engagement interventions being evaluated in terms of non-acoustic factors. That the literature has only recently identified the PEST model itself suggests that airports should not be the subject of criticism for the approach taken. They are merely on a journey of discovery in an emerging landscape that includes complex information, a range of stakeholders with different demands and requirements, concerning data that is associated with a range of interdependencies (climate change, air quality, safety issues) that make the totality of the situation airports need to describe complicated.

Considering the significant amounts of money spent by the industry on interventions such as insulation and compensation schemes, these are areas which in particular should be the focus of further research to ascertain if such investments represent good value for money in terms of increasing the QoL of residents, or whether airports could have a greater impact by investing in other areas, for instance those that may not be directly associated with noise abatement interventions [44].

It is important to note that the development of the approaches taken by airports as uncovered in this research is understandable. Firstly, the types of communication and engagement activities described as 'Best Practice' represent emerging concepts in the academic fields and so it can be expected that industry may only just be beginning to put theory into practice. Perhaps more importantly however is the fact that most airports are private enterprises with a wide number of stakeholders whose needs must be considered – not least issues of safety and complex technical data that remain essential factors in noise management. Although the aspiration of airports should be to minimise noise exposure (and other environmental impacts), based on the requirements of those who are impacted, doing so is not always feasible. This poses the question of how high up Arnstein's ladder of participation [22] airports are able to go. Although 'full Citizen Control' may be a desired state, for privately owned airports subject to significant legislative and technical constraints this may be an untenable aspiration.

That only relatively small numbers of people actually complain about airport noise means that airports must seek to expand their understanding of noise impact in affected communities. This includes the consideration of non-acoustic factors, but should also consider a range of people beyond the vocal minority who do complain. For instance, do

other people support airport activity, or simply feel unempowered to interact with the airport? How can the airport communicate with those who are motivated to act, and how does it need to engage with other stakeholders differently? What is the most appropriate balance between engaging with a wide range of people, and going more in-depth with others?

It is important to note that the cases only reviewed specific interventions and it is possible that airports are demonstrating elements of 'Best Practice' in other areas. That said, if these cases were deemed not to be representative of overall airport activity, this would indicate that such practices are not well embedded as a standard protocol. Although ANIMA has consistently highlighted the need for a flexible approach to noise management, owing to the specific characteristics of each Member State and each airport, it has also highlighted that key processes that can take an airport towards 'Best Practice' do exist, and that these should be embedded throughout all Balanced Approach interventions. Doing so is important, to maximise the potential for noise associated health impacts and constraints to be avoided. As one participant in the study stated in interview "Once you lose trust, it is almost impossible to win it back".

The ANIMA project will continue to build on these findings and to contribute to the research landscape through a number of means. A 'Best Practice Portal' is under development to help guide airport managers in how to manage noise impact more effectively. Researchers are investigating the impacts of previous noise abatement interventions on QoL and new ways of communicating noise to community members are being investigated.

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